

The evolution of preprint repositories during the Covid-19 pandemic: A temporary glitch?

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ABSTRACT

This research in progress paper investigates, whether the current preprint popularity is a temporary Covid-19 phenomenon. For this, with the help of the Dimensions database, preprints from eight repositories, namely arXiv, Authorea, bioRxiv, JMIR Preprints, medRxiv, Preprints.org, Research Square and SSRN were analyzed.

KEYWORDS

Preprints, Repositories, Publishing Behavior, Covid-19 Pandemic, Output Analysis

INTRODUCTION

The landscape of preprint repositories is diverse. There are different cultural traditions among the scientific disciplines that use preprints to disseminate scientific knowledge and to speed up the publication process. Foremost among these are the disciplines of physics and economics, which have a long tradition of using preprints in print before the first online-repositories emerged (Chiarelli et al., 2019). ArXiv, founded in 1991, was the first widely recognized repository for many scientific disciplines such as physics and computer sciences. SSRN (Social Science Research Network, founded in 1994) is the equivalent for the social sciences (Puebla et al., 2022). Most of these repositories were run initially by academics, which has partly changed in recent years with the acquisition of SSRN by Elsevier in 2016 or Research Square by Springer Nature in 2022. Later, there were also initiatives in the life sciences that resulted in bioRxiv in 2013 for the life sciences and medRxiv in 2019 for the health sciences. MedRxiv gained a lot of attention during the Covid-19 pandemic when, for example, many health scientists were eager to publish their research results as quickly as possible (Fraser, Brierley, et al., 2021). Further studies have shown that providing early access to research findings, making research articles accessible and visible to the scientific community is a strong motivation for researchers to post preprints (Fraser, Mayr, et al., 2021; Waltman et al., 2021). Additionally, the posting of preprints is a useful way to circumvent the long time lag from the submission to a journal to the official publication in a journal (Chiarelli et al., 2019). There is a citation advantage for journal articles which have been posted as a preprint (Fraser et al., 2020).

OBJECTIVES

Against this background, we investigated whether the increased posting of preprints during the Covid-19 pandemic represents a shift in the publication behavior of disciplines rather new to preprint posting such as the health sciences – or whether publishing of preprints is a rather temporary phenomenon without lasting effect. Therefore, we explored how the number of preprints has developed at different repositories and whether there are differences between Covid-19 and non-Covid-19 preprints, for example in terms of the origin of authors, the number of authors per preprint or the number of citations the preprint received. Further exploration included the identification and distribution of topics of Covid-19 preprints in the pandemic years (2020-2022). This is research in progress, as we have not been able to answer all these questions or perform advanced statistical analyses at this stage of the project.

METHODS AND DATA

To investigate the differences between Covid-19 and non-Covid-19 preprints, we selected data from repositories with a substantial number of Covid-19 preprints. To this end, in spring 2023 we retrieved all citation scores and preprints for the three pandemic years (2020-2022) for eight repositories, i.e. arXiv, Authorea, bioRxiv, JMIR Preprints, medRxiv, Preprints.org, Research Square and SSRN from the database Dimensions via API. Four of these repositories are scholar-led, the others belong to large commercial publishers. We retrieved a total of 1,195,274 preprints. After deleting 2,930 preprints with missing values (i.e., missing doi, number of authors or citation frequency), we obtained a dataset of 1,192,344 preprints. The analysis was performed with R. To distinguish between Covid-19 and non-covid-19 preprints, we used the following search string for the title of the preprints and, if available, additionally for the abstract: “coronavirus|covid-19|sars-cov|ncov-2019|2019-ncov|hcov-19|sars-2”.

RESULTS

The number of Covid-19 preprints for each repository is highest at the beginning of the pandemic in 2020 and decreases in 2021 and 2022, perhaps reflecting diminishing activity in Covid-19 research or journals increasing the publication speed (see Figure 1 left). Most preprints for Covid-19 are found on medRxiv, followed by SSRN and Research Square, which highlights the relevance of the pandemic also for research in the social sciences. The same graph for the number of non-Covid-19 preprints for each repository shows a more nuanced picture (see Figure 1

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right). At the largest repositories in terms of size, arXiv, Research Square and SSRN, the number of preprints increases slightly, at SSRN strongly. No change is observed for the other five. Among the non-Covid 19 preprints, most preprints are found on arXiv, followed by SSRN and Research Square and, with some difference, bioRxiv. Only in the case of medRxiv, far more Covid-19 preprints are posted than non-Covid-19 preprints, probably because of the thematic focus of the repository.

Figure 1. Annual Breakdown (2020-2022) of Number of Covid-19 Preprints (left) and Non-Covid-19 preprints (right) for Eight Repositories.

A look at Figure 2 (left) shows no differences between Covid-19 and non-Covid-19 preprints in terms of the number of authors per preprint (except for arXiv exposing large author numbers due to disciplines such as Particle and High Energy Physics). Figure 2 (right) shows that Covid-19 preprints have significantly higher citation numbers than non-Covid-19 preprints (as of 2023): Across repositories Covid-19 preprints received 5.14 citations on average (min=0/max=1,214/SD=22.72), while non-Covid-19 preprints received 0.31 citations on average (min=0/max=960/SD=2.15). ArXiv and Authorea show low citation counts for both types of preprints, perhaps due to the citation culture of the covered disciplines that do not formally cite preprints.

Figure 2. Preprints' Author Counts and Number of Citations in Eight Repositories published between 2020-2022.

CONCLUSION

Our preliminary results show that the sharp increase in the number of Covid-19 preprints, especially at the beginning of the pandemic in 2020, does not seem to lead to further substantial growth in preprint repositories, especially from the life sciences. Seemingly, the preprint enthusiasm does not translate to other research topics. SSRN is an exception, with a large increase in preprints in 2022, for which the reasons may vary. For all other repositories, the number of non-Covid-19 preprints reaches a plateau during the Covid-19 pandemic. It is interesting, though, that 79% of researchers have stated that after the pandemic they plan to publish some or all of their work as preprints (Biesenbender et al., 2023). Some preprints received many citations during the Covid-19 pandemic, which has, however, not led to a significant change in researchers' publishing behavior and making the posting of preprints a routine. As this is still research in progress, we want to further investigate relative ratios and normalized values for preprint and citation numbers as well as the reasons determining the decision for posting preprints, for example by analyzing the thematic differences between Covid-19 preprints in our sample. There could be also regional or disciplinary differences, as others have shown (Ni & Waltman, 2023). Also, long-term studies on how repositories develop in future are needed to ultimately answer questions on sustainability of preprint posting across disciplines.

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